

CORD-MI study on phenylketonuria (PKU)

English translation of the description in the project register of the German Portal for Medical Research Data

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Diagnoses	Phenylketonuria

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Project description

Phenylketonuria (PKU) is a congenital, hereditary disease of the protein metabolism. Due to the lack of an enzyme, the amino acid phenylalanine cannot be broken down, causing it to accumulate in the body. If left untreated, PKU can lead to neurological problems, mental retardation or health and developmental problems, for example. Thanks to comprehensive newborn screening programs and optimized therapies, almost all those affected by the disease are diagnosed and treated in good time in Germany. Nevertheless, PKU is often not sufficiently well known in adult medicine, especially among gynecologists, internists, neurologists and psychiatrists, and many people affected are therefore no longer specifically treated and cared for in adulthood. This has serious consequences and can also affect unborn children who do not suffer from the metabolic disorder themselves. However, larger systematic studies on this topic are still lacking.

Project details

Project goals

The study is being conducted to answer the following research questions based on retrospective health data:

- How often are relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric illnesses documented in combination with PKU?
- How frequently do relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric illnesses occur in combination with PKU relative to the total number of PKU patients?
- Does the relative frequency of a combination of PKU and internal, neurological and psychiatric diseases depend on age?
- How often do complications occur in PKU patients during pregnancy and childbirth? What infant outcomes can be observed?

Scientific background

Thanks to comprehensive newborn screening programs and optimized therapies, almost all those affected by PKU have been diagnosed and successfully treated in Germany since the end of the 1960s. The incidence in German-speaking countries is around 1:8,500 (on average) [1]. It must now be assumed that more than 2/3 of all people with PKU are over the age of 18. We can assume that around 5,000 people are affected in Germany. Nevertheless, PKU is often insufficiently known in adult medicine, especially among gynecologists, internists, neurologists and psychiatrists. As far as we know, many of those affected no longer receive specific treatment and care. The extent and severity of possible long-term internal, neurological and psychiatric consequences are unknown.

A few cross-sectional studies in adults with PKU show an increased incidence of relevant internal, neurological and psychiatric symptoms, which in individual cases have been associated with the presence of PKU and the quality and consistency of its treatment [2]. Larger or even systematic studies are lacking.

The most serious complication of patients with PKU treated in childhood has been known since the 1980s: embryotoxicity in mothers with PKU who were not optimally treated during pregnancy. The affected children, who themselves do not suffer from the metabolic disorder, show severe developmental and organ damage during pregnancy, depending on the quality of maternal treatment.

Literature

- Loeber, J.G., 2007. neonatal screening in Europe; the situation in 2004. *J. Inherit. Metab. Dis.* 30, 430-438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10545-007-0644-5>
- Thompson, A.J., Smith, I., Brenton, D., Youl, B.D., Rylance, G., Davidson, D.C., Kendall, B., Lees, A.J., 1990. Neurological deterioration in young adults with phenylketonuria. *Lancet* 336, 602-605. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736\(90\)93401-a](https://doi.org/10.1016/0140-6736(90)93401-a)

Material and methods

To assess comorbidities of PKU, the data is evaluated on a patient-specific basis, taking into account the ICD-10GM codes of both outpatient and inpatient presentations. The aim is to investigate whether comorbidities were ever coded for a person with PKU in the observation period 2015-2022 (according to availability). In addition to the total number of individuals with PKU, the number of patients with a comorbidity should be counted.

With regard to the observations on pregnancy and birth in women with PKU, all inpatient cases in the years 2015-2022 (according to availability) are identified in which a birth (O80, O81, O82) was coded in addition to the PKU (E70.0 and E70.1). These cases are counted cumulatively and the frequency of complications in the woman giving birth and the infant outcome parameters are summarized.

The study is conducted decentrally, with the data initially evaluated separately at each location by running centrally developed analysis scripts at the individual locations. Only the anonymous total figures are then combined centrally. As anonymity cannot be guaranteed for a total number at a location above 0 but below 6, the corresponding figures are reported as category "1 to 5". As a result, the sensitive patient data remains at the sites, but can still be used for research while maintaining privacy.

Project result

17 locations participated in the data delivery to answer the research questions. Individual results are highlighted separately below. A comprehensive scientific analysis is currently underway. PKU and comorbidities: When looking at the comorbidities of patients with PKU (as shown in the figure), it becomes clear that psychiatric disorders occur in both diagnoses (classic PKU and other hyperphenylalaninurias), including depressive episodes and recurrent depressive disorders. Occasionally, chronic kidney disease is also listed. Overall, the number of patients with documented comorbidities is very low. However, the informative value of the data is limited, as only inpatient data from patients was analyzed. However, it is to be expected that the comorbidities of patients with PKU are mainly treated in the outpatient sector.

Komorbiditäten bei PKU-Patient:innen

Bezeichnungen der ICD-10-GM-Codes

Stoffwechselstörungen

- E70.0 ... Klassische Phenylketonurie
- E70.1 ... Sonstige Hyperphenylalaninämien

Affektive Störungen

- F32.1 ... Mittelgradige depressive Episode
- F32.8 ... Sonstige depressive Episoden
- F32.9 ... Depressive Episode, nicht näher bezeichnet
- F33.0 ... Rezidivierende depressive Störung, gegenwärtig leichte Episode
- F33.1 ... Rezidivierende depressive Störung, gegenwärtig mittelgradige Episode
- F33.2 ... Rezidivierende depressive Störung, gegenwärtig schwere Episode ohne psychotische Symptome
- F33.4 ... Rezidivierende depressive Störung, gegenwärtig remittiert
- F33.8 ... Sonstige rezidivierende depressive Störungen

Sonstige degenerative Krankheiten des Nervensystems

- G31.9 ... Degenerative Krankheit des Nervensystems, nicht näher bezeichnet

Niereninsuffizienz

- N18.1 ... Chronische Nierenkrankheit, Stadium 1
- N18.2 ... Chronische Nierenkrankheit, Stadium 2
- N18.3 ... Chronische Nierenkrankheit, Stadium 3
- N18.4 ... Chronische Nierenkrankheit, Stadium 4
- N18.5 ... Chronische Nierenkrankheit, Stadium 5

Illustration 1. Distribution of comorbidities of PKU patients in the observation period 2015-2021

Data providers involved

- Charité - University Medicine Berlin
- Johann Wolfgang Goethe University Frankfurt am Main / University Hospital Frankfurt
- Klinikum rechts der Isar of the Technical University of Munich
- LMU Hospital
- Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg / University Hospital Magdeburg
- Philipps University Marburg / University Hospital Giessen / Marburg
- TU Dresden / University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus Dresden
- University of Münster / University Hospital Münster
- University Hospital Aachen
- University Hospital Erlangen
- Albrecht-Ludwig-University Freiburg / University Medical Center Freiburg
- Heidelberg University Hospital
- University Hospital Cologne
- University Hospital Regensburg
- University Hospital Tübingen
- Ulm University Hospital
- University Hospital Würzburg